

Forest of Allegory and the Allegory of Forest- Past, Present and Future: *Valli* by Sheela Tomy (Translation: Jayasree Kalathil)

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Abstract

The paper aims to explore *Valli* by Sheela Tomy as an allegory. An allegory is a paradoxical structure that simultaneously hides and reveals a fundamental tension between the surface and underlying meaning(s). The paper discusses how the novel *Valli* by Sheela Tomy is a ‘forest of allegory’ that hums the allegory of the forest. The paper tries to explore how the forest in the novel represents the ‘unrepresented and ‘unrepresentable,’ an essential tenet of allegory, and acts as a catalyst for transformation.

Keywords: Migration, Ecology, Deforestation, Folklore, Female, Home

There must come a time when each of us is able to hear the forest weep, a time when the languages of the forest and the humans will become one, a time when the axe and the chainsaw will disappear from the face of the earth. When that time comes, human beings will learn to love the earth and one another. In that time, the forest will bloom to the sound of human laughter, and it will tell us that every life, however small or delicate as touch-me-not, is divine.

It is for you, my children, that the forest weeps. (*Valli* 147)

Introduction

An allegory is a paradoxical structure that simultaneously hides and reveals a fundamental tension between the surface and underlying meaning(s). Brenda Machosky, in his *Structures of Appearing: Allegory and the Work of Literature*, defines allegory as “the appearance of one thing in another thing which it is not.” Allegory is not a mere mimetic reflection but a synthesis of real-world complexities. It offers a unique perspective. It provides

a means to represent the unrepresented and unrepresentable, those moral and political truths that defy direct expression, granting them a tangible form and allowing for deeper understanding.

Valli by Sheela Tomy, published in 2019 in Malayalam and translated into English by Jayasree Kalathil in 2022, is a forest of allegory, where the forest itself is allegorised. The author informs that ‘Valli’ holds multiple meanings in Malayalam. At first, it means vine; climbing plants. Secondly, it means Earth. Thirdly, it denotes a young woman. And lastly, it means wages, a measure of paddy given as wages (an oppressive feudal practice that exploited indigenous Adivasi people).

One can easily assume the forest is a metaphor in the novel. But the forest is not merely a descriptive metaphor in *Valli*; rather, it moves beyond its traditional metaphorical role. It serves as a catalyst that shapes the narrative's trajectory. The formulation of allegory in Judith Butler's understanding is “a way of giving a narrative form to something which cannot be directly narrativised” (11 *Vitality of Allegory*). The assimilation of that ‘something’ in ‘narrative form’ is essential as it captures the ‘rhetorical purpose’ of the writer. The forest of the novel explores that ‘something’ of the narrative. The ‘something’ of the forest embodies many things. It is a site of and for: ideas, events, predicaments, struggle, resistance, failure, victory, hope, faith and lessons. The forest in the novel collects, constructs and connects these ‘something’.

In the novel forest is not merely a geographical place; rather, it looms large as a character around which the stories of all other characters revolve. The forest shelters, shapes, guides, and rejuvenates the characters. It holds them together within its embrace, and they, in turn, carry the forest with them. The allegorical forest paves the way for other allegories- folklore, stories, home, loss, memory, destruction, capitalism, displacement, tourism, struggle, resistance and hope.

The novel, *Valli*, as an allegory, engages the writer and the readers in an ongoing act of interpretation, drawing parallels between the narrative's events with similar moments in their reality. The novel also ponders the silences of the “chronicles of generations, of development, of politics, of history...” (Tomy) and it questions: “Can those ever be sufficient to signify a land?” (Tomy). The novel embedded with silences suggests hopes for liberty.

Forest of Folklore

According to Valdimir Propp, folklore is a ‘product’ of ‘verbal art’ like literature. However, unlike literature, folklores do not have authors. It has an underlying (cultural) structure. “Folklore is the traditional, unofficial, non-institutional part of culture,” says Jan Brunvand in *The Study of American Folklore*. It is a site of traditional knowledge, values, wisdom, feelings, experiences, attitudes, beliefs, etc., recorded orally and disseminated down the ages. The novel has folk elements- local tales, folk songs, etc., showcasing the culture of indigenous people or *Adivasis*.

In the novel's core, the folktale of Unniyachi, a *devdasi* or dancing concubine of gods throbs. Historically, in literature, her presence can be found in Champu poetry of olden times.

Iravivarman, the king of Bayaland (land of paddy fields) that later becomes Wayanad, is captivated by Unniyachi, the courtesan. They make love. Iravivarman's touch "liberates her slowly, languidly, from her clothes" (3). Their carnal cravings are fleeting, as Iravivarman has to return to his duty as a ruler. He can be with her till the eighth day in the month of Khumbham. As per the myth, on the day of the festival, the king gifts her a necklace of eighteen rubies as a token of his love. The necklace can also be seen as the payment for her services to him. When she performs on the stage on the day of the festival, she locks eyes with a man in the audience. His gaze asks her, "Have you forgotten me?" The man, a lower-caste sculptor, was hired by the king to carve the stones of the wall. He carves lovemaking scenes. While she is dancing, his gaze makes her restless. He seems to be part of her. She falls in love with him. She pines to meet him. On the ninth day of the festival, she secretly "meets him "avoiding the ruler and his soldiers" (4) in the temple. They meet, and just like the figures carved on the wall, "in the flickering light of a lamp on a low stool, dancing figures move lasciviously on the stone pillars" (4). He completes her, and their connection is from the previous birth. When the king knows about them, Unniyachi is brought back to him, manacled. She throws the necklace of eighteen rubies on the floor, and in a fit of anger, he kills her with his sword. The broken necklace, its eighteen rubies that rolled in different directions, gave birth to a life-filled islet and "someone named the islet Kuruvadweep" (4). The creation of the islet is protected by the canopy of the 'mighty tree', which holds the 'water of wisdom.' This leads to the freedom of Unniyachi as she "flies away into the heaven above" (4). After the death of Unniyachi, the *devdasi* system ends, and Unniyachi becomes the deity of the aboriginal. Moreover, Unniyachi "lives on in each female child born in the village" (4).

The story of Unniyachi in the novel amalgamates myth, folklore, imagery and real locations, creating an allegorical narrative of creation and transformation. The created land is diverse and fertile, where there is life and growth ready for new beginnings, symbolised by the flowing water (islet) and protected by the wisdom and protection of the 'mighty tree'. The ascension of Unniyachi to heaven adds an allegorical dimension which connects the land (Wayanad) to the divine (Heaven). The cultural wisdom of *Adivasis* boils down to the present through this mythical folktale.

The allegorical presence of Unniyachi is witnessed in the novel, from the beginning to the end, through different characters. Unniyachi is embedded in them, and they resonate with Unniyachi. She provides strength and shows light to people of all four generations fighting different battles against injustice in different ways.

In the epilogue of the novel, Unniyachi appears again. She, in the epilogue, puts a post on Facebook. Unniyachi of the Facebook post is fourth generation Tessa, who takes the essence of Unniyachi, the mythical character, her mother and the forest along with her. Through the Facebook post, she informs the world about the furious flood of 2018, which washed away the

sins of capitalism, exploitation, and man-accelerated destruction, suggesting hope for new beginnings.

Tessa gives life to Unniyachi through her life. Through Unniyachi, she brings the struggles of the forest, a neighbouring village, Kalluvayal and its people to light in the world. She also tries to provide a framework to overcome the struggles of her time. Unniyachi is a bridge that connects her to Wayanad, its forest and her people living there.

Voicing the Forest and the Female Voice

The allegorical narratives consist of a ‘main object’ that constructs the ‘literal narrative’ behind which there is a ‘figural intent’ whose recognition fulfils the ‘rhetorical purpose’. This ‘quadripartite structure’ characterises all allegorical narratives.

In *Valli*, the ‘main object,’ forest and females, construct the ‘literal narrative.’ The ‘literal narrative’ is set in *Wayanad*, a region in the Western Ghats of Kerala. The novel records the living history of four generations of families who made *Wayanad* their home, reflecting the evolution of the place and its people through diary entries, mails and narrated stories. Through the diary entries of Susan, Tessa gets to know about the environmental, social, political, economic and religious landscape of *Wayand*.

The narrative of *Valli* is about the uprooting of women and the forest. Sara, the second-generation woman (the first generation being the migrants who settled there), had to flee to Wayanad to live with Thommichan, as her family was against their relationship. Their marital union takes place in the forest. Susan, their daughter, leaves the abode of the forest to live in Abu Dhabi, the ‘forest of desert’, with Shayam, but previously she loved James. James also loved her but never expressed it to her. When James showed no affection and chose the forest as his life’s mission, she accepted Shyam’s proposal of marriage. Shayam later abandons Susan and Tessa (their daughter) and starts a new life in the ‘city of lights’ anew. In the dry, harsh land, Susan builds a career for herself in sustainable architecture. She pines for her land, forest and river where she spent her childhood. She alone cared for her daughter and gave her wings to soar high. Tessa represents the fourth and present generation. She is pursuing a university education. Along with Saif, she is working on a robot named Betty. The literal narrative also explores the lives of Lucy, Isabella, Kali and Pembli.

Lucy, an *adiyaan*, marries Peter, the son of *jenmi*, the landlord, Ivachan. After their marriage, Anjilikkunnil abandons them. They take shelter in Padmanabhan’s house. A boy named James, later Joymon, is born to them. Lucy loses both Joymon and Peter. Joymon dies, and Peter disappears. The waves of grief never leave her heart.

Isabella, Peter’s sister, also holds loss and grief deep in her heart as her husband is murdered by her other brother. She complains about him and puts him behind bars. She, too, leaves Anjilikkunnil and joins the missionary. Years later, when she returns, the glory of Anjilikkunnil has diminished to the ruins of injustice, which she tries to bring back to life.

Kali, a madwoman, ferocious as the goddess Kali is first disowned by her parents and later is raped and killed.

Pembi, the indigenous medicine woman, disappears with the growth of the herbal medicine industry, and the authorities take no action to find her.

The forest shares the same fate as these women, first due to timber merchants and then because of the flourishing of tourism in Wayanad.

Through the above-discussed characters, the narrative attains its 'figural intent'. *Valli* intends to show that gender, nature and power are intricately intertwined and construct the disposition of dualism. A society with systemic gender bias propagates dualism, which equates nature with female and, therefore, passive and inferior, whereas it associates male with the urban environment, representing progress and power. Females and forests have been treated like 'passive objects' of possession and therefore silenced, suppressed, violated and exploited.

The 'figural intent' of the narrative achieves its 'rhetorical purpose' by 'voicing the forest' and 'giving a female a voice' that speaks of injustice. Despite all the injustices, the females and the forest achieve victory in the novel. Sara lives a life that guides the other females and males around her. The school, Kadoran School, where she teaches, helps the indigenous children reclaim their language, culture and beliefs with pride. Susan leaves a legacy of resistance against sexual violence and injustice. She also sows the seed of love for the forest, stories and people in her daughter. Lucy stands firm against exploitation, and Isabella holds perseverance in her character. Kali's existence is itself a revolt, and Pembi embodies indigenous wisdom. Lastly, the forest looms large as a site for resilience, transformation and regeneration.

The novel successfully achieves its purpose by presenting female characters as allegorical externalisation of the struggles of the forest. In this continuous interconnectedness and engagement, the narrative builds solidarity between the forest and the females.

Forest, a Home

Harrison quotes Giambattista Vico in *Forests: The Shadow of Civilization*, who asserts that in "the order of human institutions" (245), the forests come first, after which come the huts, then the villages. The next in the series are the cities, and last comes the academies. The novel sustains this idea.

The forest, the protagonist of the novel, is home not only to flora and fauna but also provides shelter to forgotten histories, *adivasis*, migrants, the deserted, stories and hope. It gives freedom to animals and humans to coexist. The relationship between Toto, the monkey and Basavan and Lucy speaks for the harmony of coexistence. The forest has also witnessed the inculcation of love, which has deepened the love for the forest. As the forest recreates and regenerates, the culture of indigenous people, which is close to nature worship, also celebrates the first menstruation cycle of a female.

In the freedom and divine mysticism of the forest, folktales resonate, and it also hums with folksongs. The lost and dead are present and alive in the murmur and memories of the forest. Peter disappears into the forest and never returns. But his spark and rebellious nature flow in the wind of the forest. Basavan, “the protector, the hugger of wild trees” (42 Tomy), dies while fighting for the cause and life of the forest. In return, the forest mourns and remembers him as a martyr.

The destruction of the forest parallels the destruction of the home. Anjilikkunnil, the house of *Jenmis*, fails to become a home. It witnesses a downfall as it thrives on exploitation and injustice. The patriarchs of the house flourished in past by exploiting the forest and the females. Whereas Manjadikunnu, the red-stoned house- the dream of Sara, flourishes with time and creates a space for laughter, joy, progress, transformation and peace. It becomes a home not only for descendants of Sara and Thommichan but also for James. The 2018 flood washed away everything, including Anjilikkunnil. But the red-stoned house “by the river stands, unshaken, even after the visit of the furious water” (391).

The forest is not only a physical space but is rather an abstract concept that keeps changing its meaning. The continuous shift of meanings creates an allegory that plays an important role in the progress of the narrative.

Custodian of Forest and Future

In chapter one, Introduction – The Crooked Timber of Humanity, in the book *New Perspectives on People and Forests*, Dainis Dauksta mentions a Russian proverb by Anon, which says, “He who looks backwards to history is blind in one eye, but he who looks only forward is blind in both eyes” (3).

Through *Valli*, Sheela Tomy, makes the present generation, Tessa in the narrative and readers in reality, the custodians of the forest and future. She implores us not to forget the past and learn from it for a green and liberated future.

Conclusion

In a nutshell, the novel is a forest of allegory in which the forest is allegorised. The forest, an allegorical site, holds together folklore, female, family, friends and the future. It adds value to human life and draws a parallel between the destruction of the forest and the destruction of human life.

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